

Mapping Mobility: A community vehicle to pollution abatement

Final project report

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ACTION Accelerator

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Introduction to the project:

The 'Mapping Mobility' project takes a citizen science approach to engaging communities in active travel and Geographical Information Systems (GIS). The project was initially conceived under the realisation that community-led incentives towards participating in an active travel project may help increase the uptake and subsequent usage of such modes. In turn, this would help to alleviate local air pollution and help facilitate the transition to low carbon modes of mobility.

Project aim:

The project aimed to assess if participation in a collective, community-led project situated around active travel might help incentivise local transitions towards low-pollution modes. At the same time, the data collected by the community would also provide key insights into local travel behaviours – particularly the main routes of travel utilised by a community. This data could also be analysed by the community to not only better understand the realities of active travel in their community, but to also better communicate the *challenges* of active travel to appropriate governance structures and local groups. As such, there was direct stakeholder impact embedded into these approaches.

Project approach:

In order to accomplish the above aim, the project created three key roles for the community to engage with – data collectors, community engagers and data analysts.

Figure 1 - The three roles offered by the Mapping Mobility project.

As a summary of these roles:

- **Data collectors** have been collecting spatial data regarding their active travel routes. This could be by walking, cycling, running, mobility scooter, or any other feasible mean. Participants have been collecting this data by either (1) using the app 'map my tracks' and providing a 'tag' to identify which travel mode they had used, or (2) providing previous data from other apps, such as Strava. Participants were then invited to attend a workshop to discuss the data further.
- **Community engagers** are individuals that would promote the project within the community, to help design engaging materials which promoted active travel and to assist in project recruitment. This role was created to offer the opportunity to engage in the project for those who might not want to engage in active travel, or those who may feel digitally excluded from being unable to participate in the data analyst role (see below). Unfortunately, there were no participants that signed up to this role.

- **Data analysts** were trained to use GIS software through a series of self-guided video lectures and practicals. They then inherited the data collected by **data collectors** and created a map to illustrate the key findings.

Participants collected data between the 01/06/21 and the 20/08/21. Data was analysed between 20/08/21 and 26/08/21.

Project location and context:

This project was situated in Rugeley, Staffordshire in the United Kingdom. Rugeley is an ex-mining and historic market town community of approximately 21,000 residents.

The Mapping Mobility project is situated within a wider £3 million Innovate UK funded project – Zero Carbon Rugeley. This project, which is part of the Prospering From the Energy Revolution (PFER) program, aims to design a zero carbon future for the town, with a specific focus on decarbonising local transport/ mobility. One such focus is around the promotion of active travel and redevelopment of the town to be more active travel 'friendly'. Thus, the data collected through this process, which will continue after the Accelerator period, will be used to better understand how to cater the design

Project results:

Project limitations:

Covid-19:

- Despite best efforts, this project took place during a difficult time in the midst of the Covid-19 pandemic. It proved particularly difficult to recruit people to this project, even with financial incentives. We suspect this was due to there being 'other priorities' to address during these times.

Running the project within the ACTION Accelerator timeframe:

- The 6-month timescale of the project proved difficult to meet from a university institution. This was firstly due to the timescales of obtaining ethical approval from Keele University, which prevented us from being able to do any research or recruitment. There were technological limitations with emails which slowed this further. Secondly, the University was responding to the Covid-19 pandemic and undergoing internal restructuring, which slowed the progress of hiring our graduate research assistant to the project.
- Another issues was how much participants were being asked to do. The embedding of surveys and workshops, as well as participation in the project generally, proved to be a deterrent.

Technological issues:

- Participants would often face technological issues with their own devices or the app itself. This was often due to how their own device was set up, which made troubleshooting by the research team particularly difficult. Otherwise, there were regular IOS and Android updates which would interfere with the functionality of the app. In one instance, this deterred an individual from continuing in participating.

- The app we selected to use was the easiest to integrate with QGIS software **at the time** of project design. We selected this app in order to make the entire project easier to run for the citizen scientists. In particular, working with a smaller company to develop a 'bulk data download' function also fit better with the 6 month timescales. However, this meant incentivising people on to new apps which they may not feel comfortable using. Approximately 4 months into the accelerator period, other apps (such as Strava) would become easier to integrate with QGIS.
- There was a spam attack on the Map My Tracks server, which resulted in some individuals receiving spam messages. This was quickly resolved by the Tinderhouse team (within 12 hours) and seemingly had no impact on participation.

A complex mix of the above factors at different stages in the project inevitably has limited engagement thus far. However, participation is growing. As of the 18/08/21, we have collected 31.2km of active travel routes, with a total of seven data collectors and two

Project impact:

This accelerator project has helped enhance the rate at which this project would have been developed. Because of this, the potential of this project can now be realised. We are already seeing a significant amount of interest in this type of approach. Key impacts include:

- Interest from 'Connected Places Catapult' in developing this approach further, as well as joint collaboration on an academic paper at the Decarbon8 conference in September to showcase embedding citizen science approaches with traditional transport modelling strategies to develop a more nuanced place-based assessment of active travel in communities.
- Working with Rugeley Town Council to further promote this project locally and to stitch it into other active travel projects and initiatives locally, including future bids for active travel infrastructure at St Augustines Church and Rugeley Rugby Club. These bids aim to promote cycling to and from this area and to reduce the number of parked cars in cycle lanes.

- Working with Cannock Chase District Council to embed the Mapping Mobility project into their 'Cannock Chase Can' district health improvement plans. This will eventually see the integration of this approach with a new district app, with the approaches subsequently being rolled out across the district.

Thus, whilst recruitment may have been limited thus far and in this particular instance, there is clear interest in the approaches the accelerator has helped shape, with citizen science participation being a clear interest for local stakeholders.

Recommendations for future projects:

There were key learnings regarding how to run a project of this type.

- Firstly, we recommend developing an app, rather than using one created by an external organisation. This allows for a quicker assessment of any technological issues which may arise. Similarly, the characteristics of the app and its functionality can be better steered for the purposes of the project. However, the project teams should be flexible and able to receive data from other suitable apps.
- A distinctive 'data manager' role is needed and separate from a role which manages 'community engagement'. Diversifying and breaking down these research roles is important to ensure the project team have the capacity to focus their attention where required and at a more consistent pace.
- Secondly, we suggest that a timeframe of 6 months will not be enough to run the Mapping Mobility project. Despite the institutional problems we encountered (which are specific to our circumstances), encouraging individuals to engage in active travel is difficult. Even with an pre-established network of Community Gatekeepers who helped promote the project widely, recruitment was difficult.
- Thirdly, a limitation of this project has been trying to operate and engage the community in an 'in situ' activities using online approaches and methods. We suggest that 'community mapping days' where locals can get together to would be a good incentive.

Concluding thoughts and future directions for the Mapping Mobility project:

Whilst the project had not progressed to the extent we would have liked, the ACTION Accelerator has nonetheless sped up the development of this project and led to a number of key lessons learned. We fully intend to continue with this research project, particularly given the interest in it from local authorities in Staffordshire and from the Zero Carbon Rugeley consortium. It is our belief that with a few more months we can develop a detailed insight into active travel in the Rugeley community, as well as make a number of refinements to the approach.

We are excited by the interest in these approaches from local stakeholders. With their backing, the project (and subsequent participation in it) will undoubtedly continue to grow.

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